

From Concept to Collaboration: The Arctic Acoustic Observing Network

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Why do we need an Arctic Acoustic Observing Network?

Global climate change has already had significant observable effects on the environment. Nowhere are the consequences of the Anthropocene epoch more apparent than in the Arctic, where warming is occurring disproportionately compared to the rest of the planet (e.g. Rantanen et al. 2022). Rapid, extreme reductions in Arctic sea ice extent, age, and thickness are driving cascading effects in Arctic ecosystems from physical oceanography to marine predators reliant on a stable, ice-based ecosystem. The impacts from these changes are reflected in the life histories, migratory timing, and biogeographic distribution (i.e., northward expansions or range constrictions) of marine fish, birds, and mammals (e.g. Laidre et al. 2015, Moore et al. 2019). Concurrently, vessel traffic is increasing in many Arctic regions, raising concerns about impacts of underwater noise on marine species, including whales and seals. These changes all may impact Arctic inhabitants who rely on many of these species for nutritional, cultural and spiritual subsistence (Huntington et al. 2020). One way to monitor these changes is by listening to them. Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) has the advantage of providing seasonally unbiased, multi-year data over a broad range of frequencies and spatial scales, even at remote and (seasonally) inaccessible locations. Hydrophones can be deployed year-round and record even

under ice and during the polar night when more traditional methods of studying marine animals are not feasible. Hence, passive acoustic data can be used to understand changes in the phenologies of Arctic endemic species as well as document the potential borealization of the Arctic (e.g. Stafford 2019, Szesciorka & Stafford 2023).

In the spirit of the Southern Ocean Hydrophone Network (van Opzeeland et al. 2013), here we propose a similar acoustic network that covers as much of the Arctic Ocean as possible. The Arctic Acoustic Observing Network (AAON) aims to better understand seasonal noise levels and how they are changing, to describe and document human use of the Arctic and changes in biodiversity, presence, and migratory patterns of Arctic and subarctic species.

In 2019, the Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF) initiated a pan-Arctic metadatabase of passive acoustic monitoring data holders. The initial results of this showed that there have been many tens of hydrophone deployments throughout the Arctic (with the exception being in Russian Federation waters). Although incomplete at the time, this effort highlighted the potential to establish a (semi)pan-Arctic network through international collaborations. To this end, we held a workshop in 2025 at the Arctic Science Summit Week in Boulder, Colorado, to initiate the AAON with a small group of researchers working on Arctic PAM, which we intend to expand in the process of moving forward with establishing the AAON.

The overall goal of this network is to bring together data holders to establish the AAON as a collaborative pan-Arctic PAM effort. Our first aim is to identify data sources and gaps in acoustic coverage of the Arctic, look for ways to fill those gaps, and identify other partners for the observing network. Next steps include agreeing on common metrics to measure and report, developing a library of detectors that can be used to analyse large datasets, and examining large-scale patterns in the Arctic Ocean soundscapes, i.e. in biophony (all biological sounds by soniferous (sound-producing) animals), geophony (all naturally occurring, non-biological sounds) and anthrophony (all sounds produced by humans). The AAON has the potential to provide semi-pan Arctic marine mammal distributions including endemic Arctic species but also acoustically active subarctic species, and also contribute to international efforts on global ocean sound monitoring (Tyack et al. 2023).

We envision the AAON to function similarly to, and be incorporated into, the Pan-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory (PAN-DBO)¹ which is a framework for international research coordination wherein partners agree to repeat sampling at designated stations and share data openly during national and international research voyages to the Arctic. The DBO was originally envisioned as a 'change detection array' and biological observatory from north to south in the Pacific Arctic. It has since expanded to the Atlantic with DBOs in Davis Strait-Baffin Bay, the Siberian and Atlantic Arctic giving the DBOs a Pan-Arctic reach.

¹ <https://oceandecade.org/actions/pan-arctic-distributed-biological-observatory/>

Figure 1. Map of past and present locations of hydrophones deployed in the Arctic from 2001-2022. These data represent submissions from over 25 different organizations. Green circles indicate short term deployments (< 1 year) while blue circles indicate longer term deployments (> 1 year). The deployment map and metadata are archived and available on open access at: [Arctic PAM database by CAFF](#).

To date, over two dozen organizations have provided metadata for their hydrophone deployments as part of the CAFF effort mentioned above. Figure 1 shows the locations of 368 hydrophone deployments from 2001 to 2022. The CAFF database is currently being updated, and any additional deployment information is being solicited from colleagues.

Although the locations in Figure 1 represent different instruments with different sampling rates and duty cycles, there are many ways in which the data can be combined to study pan-Arctic patterns. As one example, Clark et al. (2015) analysed data from six different research groups to depict a year in the life of Bering-Chukchi-Beaufort bowhead whales from 2009/2010 as part of the Synthesis of Arctic Research. From 114 possible hydrophone sites in the Pacific Arctic, the common resolution among them was at least one recording every 12 hours. For the analysis, at least one bowhead whale call was required in a 12-hours period for all datasets. Using a sector approach rather than an individual site approach, made it easier to compare detections overall. Joining forces will allow the AAON to increase our understanding of patterns of occurrence of vocal marine species as well as patterns of ambient noise across Arctic environments. As part of the AAON workshop in 2025, we developed ideas for a pan-Arctic analysis of two marine mammal species and noise metrics (soundscape descriptions).

In the end, it was decided that both bearded seals and bowhead whales would be tractable species for regional comparisons using data from 2017-2024. Next steps will include determining which year(s) are appropriate, which entails querying the CAFF dataset for locations, durations, sample rates and duty cycles.

One of the most tractable products that can arise from an acoustic network is an understanding of the underwater soundscape (noise metrics) at different locations and times of year. Given that 'ocean sound' is now an 'Essential Ocean Variable' to measure per the Global Ocean Observing System (Tyack et al. 2023), we agreed on meaningful and (where applicable) internationally recommended metrics that allow comparability across studies, locations and years. These include:

Sound Pressure Levels (SPL) in:

- a. 1/3 octave bands at 63, 250, and 2000 Hz
- b. 1 Hz bins averaged over 5 min (including SPL percentiles)
- c. a broadband (20 Hz –10 kHz) frequency range

Sound Exposure Levels (SEL)

The 1/3 octave bands at 63 and 250 Hz bandwidth are recommended for monitoring ship noise in the European Union by the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, Dekeling et al. 2014). In addition to the lower and broadband frequencies, the hearing ranges or acoustic bandwidths of Arctic marine animals need to be included, for instance higher frequency components for bowhead whales and narwhals at > 2 kHz. SEL was added because it is important to assess the potential impact of noise on animals. Root Mean Square SPLs provide the noise levels of different instruments including the noise floor and the effect of wind on noise levels, as two examples. Percentiles are important for understanding the noise floor and comparing among instruments which can temper the understanding of absolute sound measurements. For instance, Halliday et al. (2021) compared 1/3 octave levels at 15 locations in the Canadian Arctic to examine spatial and temporal trends of noise. They used data from 6 different instrument types with varied sample rates and duty cycles to explain daily sound

pressure levels as well as comparing patterns in months with high levels of shipping to those without.

Next steps toward a collaborative workflow of PAM data analysis will include:

- identifying appropriate periods with a maximum acoustic coverage of the Arctic Ocean to be analysed,
- testing and applying existing detectors for the two key species on the identified datasets,
- quantifying ocean sound, including anthropogenic noise, in the Arctic Ocean by calculating and reporting the above mentioned metrics, and
- providing the outcomes of these first AON case studies on an open access basis through a suitable portal.

Conclusions

The Arctic Acoustics Observing Network is moving from an idea to a reality. We believe that one of the best ways to monitor broad underwater Arctic regions and understand how these are changing with continued warming is to use PAM. Because the Arctic is not homogenous, and changes are evidenced in different ways in different regions, pan-Arctic monitoring is imperative. This short white paper serves to inform the communities of the Arctic Science Summit and Arctic Observing Summit about the existence of AON in the hopes of continued and new collaborations between research groups and Arctic nations to collect, analyze and interpret passive acoustic data from the Arctic.

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